

Sustainable Solutions: Transforming Textile Waste from Design to Marketing

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Abstract:

Background: Every year, India generates more than 7,793 tonnes of textile waste, accounting for 8.5% of the global total. Due to issues with quality and visibility, only a small portion of this waste—59%—finds its way back into the worldwide supply chains for high-end goods in the textile sector. The “Waste to Wealth” report, which was released in July 2022, provides an outline of the potential and challenges India is facing regarding the flow of textile waste as well as the various subtitles of the country’s developing circular economy.

Methods: This study describes several kinds of pre-consumer synthetic textile waste accessible in the textile industry for conversion into functional recycled value-added products. Synthetic textile waste is converted into fibers, which are then used to make product which promotes eco-cycle solutions. From starting from collecting synthetic textile waste from the textile industry to development of recycled outcomes.

Results: The findings revealed that fibre derived from synthetic textile waste is highly valued and accepted in terms of long-term growth in the textile industry.

Conclusion: This research represents a minor step towards the textile industry's sustainable growth. Furthermore, this type of venture will help to drive economic development. The goal is to recycle synthetic textile waste to the extent that it is non-biodegradable.

Keywords: Fibers, Recycling, Sustainable, Synthetic, Textiles, Value-added product

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1. Introduction

Recycling is essential, as we all know that the textile sector is the second most polluting industry. By collecting synthetic textile waste and processing various sorts of pre-consumer textile waste that would otherwise end up in landfills as garbage, the robust system will reprocess them into materials or goods for the development of value-added products. Recycling textile waste will benefit not just the environment, but also the textile industry's economic development. As it's rightly said, “Be part of the solution, not part of pollution”. This technique aims to design and manufacture home furnishings using materials that have a lesser environmental impact than fashion products, with an emphasis on creating products that consumers like, feel connected to, and want to keep and use. The rapid evolution of fashion has led to an increase in both fabric manufacture and waste generation. The environmental impacts of textile production, use, and disposal are well-documented. The textile industry is shifting from the "take-make-waste" model to a circular economy. This effort aims to reintegrate textiles into the product lifecycle, reducing waste and creating a sustainable loop that saves resources and reduces environmental impact. As a result, the process of valorizing fabric company waste to salvage fibres and create high-value products has been increasingly popular. Textile waste is valorized through three phases: pretreatment, enzymatic hydrolysis, and fiber regeneration. After the fiber has been retrieved from synthetic textile trash, it can be used to make new value-added products. The apparel and textile industries' growth and rapid fashion demand have led to a significant increase in textile waste, with 75% landfilled and 25% recycled. Consumer awareness, closed-loop circular systems, and innovative textile recycling technologies are needed to promote sustainable consumption [1].

2. Materials and Methods

Synthetic Textile Waste is used as a primary material for the fiber-to-fiber recycling and production of value-added products to market in the sustainable community market. Fibres in textile products are commonly made up of bi- or multi-component yarns with mixed components. Products are functionalised by combining the properties of fibre

components with this material mixture. Fibre construction expands the range of product materials (clothing textiles), including haberdashery (zip, button, bias binding), multilayer constructions (membrane, lining, or wadding on jacket), functional coatings (water-repellent coating), dyes, prints, and practices. One prerequisite for sustainable recycling is to make the material flow as pure and suitable as possible. The mixing of components in this process can create barriers or make recycling uneconomical, non-natural, or technologically impractical [2]. A sustainable design strategy for producing a value-added product from synthetic textile waste composite material by mixing waste textiles and other components. Synthetic textile wastes are non-biodegradable, the extension of recycling the waste to reduce the waste material and produce economic development, providing a long-term, environmentally beneficial option for minimizing pollution and waste [3].

Synthetic fibre recycling can be carried out against textile wastes whose composition and internal structure are primarily made up of synthetic and/or artificial fibres. Nylon/polyamide, polyester, elastomer, or acrylic are materials used by textile and hosiery manufacturers and laboratories to make consumer items such as socks, knitwear, and garments.

2.1 Starting from collecting synthetic textile waste from the textile industry.

There have been numerous suggestions for collecting the pile of old fabric people need to get rid of. There are different options available for the collection of synthetic textile waste.

Table 1 - Options for collection of Synthetic Textile Waste

The fashion industry faces significant structural challenges, requiring a paradigm shift. Agamben's concept of intempestivity aids in resilience, promoting innovation and sustainability. Case studies demonstrate successful changes through recycling, upcycling, material circularity, and textile waste valorisation. The study explores post-consumer waste dynamics and upcycling processes' effectiveness in sustainable transformation, aiming to shift the textile/clothing sector's paradigm between sustainable logic and recycling design. Fashion and Textile Design explores post-consumer waste dynamics, revealing upcycling processes' effectiveness in long-term transformation. This shift between sustainable logic and recycling design perspectives is reflected in the textile/clothing sector [4]. Textile waste is segregated according to fabric type, quality, and applicability. Sorting textile waste is crucial for successful textile recycling since it determines the quality and quantity of recycled fibres and products. It is

problematic since the textile waste streams contain a variety of fabrics, colours, patterns, and contaminants. Technologies have been developed to help separate textile waste. One of the technologies incorporates hyperspectral imaging and artificial intelligence. It employs a camera that can photograph textile waste in a variety of wavelengths and lighting conditions. The images are then fed into an algorithm, which examines and classifies the fabric based on fibre content and contaminants. This approach allows for high precision and speed for sorting textile waste [5]. Emerging technology solutions, such as re-polymerization, can enhance textile recycling efficiency by reducing PET to its molecular level, subsequently polymerizing it to create new fibers.

2.2 Determining end use of textile waste in community.

Table 2 - End-use of textile waste split by waste streams

End Use	Pre- Consumer (of 3265 ktons)	Domestic post-consumer (of 3944 ktons)	Imported (of 584 ktons)
Reuse	16% is being used, the current production process primarily consists of surplus fabrics and garments from overproduction (66%), with a small amount coming from cutting and mill waste.	51% clothing is being repurposed, sorted, and sold at secondhand markets.	16% is being re-exported to other countries as secondhand apparel. These re-exports primarily consist of clean, trendy, lightweight apparel that is in high demand in tropical African and Asian countries.
Recycle	46% is being recycled. The recycling of waste primarily consists of fibre waste (86%), cutting waste (10%), and mill waste (4%), indicating that a significant portion of this waste is utilized in various applications.	4% is getting recycled. India's recycling of non-wearables is limited to pre-consumer and imported garbage, as non-wearables are highly contaminated in this waste stream.	47 % is recycled and accounts for a significant amount of woollen and acrylic waste, as these materials are not in high demand in nations that accept secondhand apparel. It also comprises polluted and mangled cotton-rich materials that cannot be worn.
Downcycle	37% is being downcycled, this primarily includes cutting waste, mill waste, and fiber waste.	2% of material is being utilized for the production of wipes and as filling for bedding and quilts.	36% waste is being downcycled into non-textile sectors, including wipes and bedding fillers, which are used domestically and exported for international manufacturing.
Incineration/ Disposal	1% is being burned or landfilled.	43% Does not make its way back into the textile business, with a large portion being burnt and landfilled.	1% is known to be burnt for energy, significantly going to landfills, possibly due to high import costs and stakeholder desire for maximum value.

Table Source [6]

Textile recycling can help reduce waste by extending product life and designing materials for circularity. Our goal is to create a sustainable and comprehensive textile waste management system that enables efficient collection, recovery, reuse, and recycling of textile materials. Textile waste management requires collaboration among producers, recycling centres, brands, consumers, and public agencies. Implementing innovative technologies and

efficient and sustainable collection and sorting systems is a vital step towards accomplishing these objectives and promoting the highest level of sustainability. The projects aim to convert textile waste into raw materials, use more mechanically recycled fibres, overcome technical problems in thermo-mechanical recycling, and create capsule collections with post-consumer recycled items. Recover™, a mechanical recycling leader, is devoted to developing systems, standards, and physical tests to close the textile loop in Europe. Currently, it mostly uses post-industrial textiles as raw materials. Mechanically recycled fibres, including Recover™ RColorBlend, are a sustainable alternative to virgin fibres that minimise CO2 emissions without post-production treatments.

A product's ability to be recyclable is determined by its material, separation methods, and recycling stages. Using integrated methodologies and tools to build sustainable clothing systems leads to innovative and sustainable solutions.

2.3 Retrieving fibre from the textile waste

Textiles that are disposed of in landfills represent lost value and remain there since landfills are meant to hold rather than decompose. Organic matter degrades in landfills by anaerobic decomposition, which is mediated by microbes and produces methane and carbon dioxide. The extent to which a material, such as glucose, degrades is determined by the microbial population present at the landfill site [8]. When the necessary facilities are available, some textiles are burned to generate electricity. Waste textiles discarded in the environment through incorrect disposal or partial disintegration may accumulate or decompose, depending on the circumstances. To redirect solid food and paper waste from traditional landfills to alternative biological waste treatment options, the European Commission landfill Directive defined "biodegradable waste" as "any waste that is food and green waste, as well as paper and paperboard, can decompose either anaerobically or aerobically." Melt reprocessing, chemical/enzymatic conversion, and biological conversion are all examples of industrial processing techniques. Circular processes recover useful components from waste while reducing waste material loss to the environment.

Fibre can be retrieved using the amber cycling approach. Amber cycling uses a biological recycling to regenerate materials from post-consumer trash. The process involves regenerating polyester into yarn, transforming T-shirts into new fibers, reducing landfill waste, and reducing the need for fresh materials [7].

A textile engineer from RWTH Aachen University in Germany, products created with man-made fibres or synthetic blends can be recycled using one of four methods:

i) Mechanical recycling (tear)

Mechanical textile recycling is the process of shredding textile fabric and recycling it into fibres without the use of chemicals. The carding process produces yarn for knitted or woven materials. Textiles with mechanical damage are cut into smaller pieces and fed into a garnett machine for carding. The collected fibres are blended with virgin fibres at varying rates, resulting in a finer yarn. Recycled yarn is 15-18% cheaper than virgin fiber, impacting fabric prices.

ii) Thermal-mechanical recycling (regranulation)

Thermo-mechanical recycling (regranulation) is a method that involves melting, filtering, and extruding synthetic fibres or textiles as input material. Thermo-mechanical recycling is a method for reusing post-industrial wastes by melting plastic with built-in heating elements and frictional heat, removing volatile substances, and subsequently cooled before being chopped into short strands, potentially reducing resource costs and trash disposal.

iii) Physicochemical recycling (solvent-based separation)

Physicochemical recycling uses solvent-based separation to separate synthetic/natural fibers, convert them into RePAN pellets, and spin until primary fiber is obtained, reclaiming polymer waste streams, producing virgin plastic quality, and achieving high-grade polymer characteristics.

iv) Chemical recycling (returning to Oligomer/monomer)

Chemical recycling converts polymers into oligomers or monomers, producing virgin quality products with no physical loss. Procedures for PET textiles include hydrolysis, alcoholysis, and aminolysis, making it superior to mechanical recycling in technology. Filtration/separation purifies oligomers or monomers, converting them into polymers or chemicals. This yields high-quality secondary raw materials for spinning and textile fibre production.

Table 3 - Schematic path of deconstruction, disintegration, and degradation results

Table Source [8]

Microbial composting totally degrades natural fibres, while some plastics have been developed to do the same. However, process pollutants in bioplastics can cause ecotoxicity. Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a waste-to-energy process that generates biogas (methane) by digesting organic wastes such as manure, municipal wastewater, agricultural residues, and food waste. AD procedures typically require liquid slurries (< 20% solids) as feedstocks, which is uncommon for waste textiles. Proposed processes for converting textile waste and evaluating the digestibility of plastic waste in AD and landfill conditions have been reviewed. Natural and manufactured textile fibres are semi-crystalline, containing both amorphous and crystalline areas. This crucial feature gives textile fibres a combination of toughness and strength [9]. The initial disintegration and degradation of fibres occurs in amorphous regions, which are more accessible to water and other chemicals due to their increased free volume, causing fibres to break apart into minute pieces and microfibers. When materials biodegrade in the environment, minute fragments depolymerise into low molecular weight molecules that microorganisms consume for energy and convert to carbon dioxide and water. Some molecules are turned into biomass, which forms the cells. Fibres and plastic materials can resist degradation, disrupting the full degradation pathway and causing environmental accumulation.

2.4 Development of recycled outcomes

a. Shoes made by Kwabena Obiri Yeboah KoliKoWear, Ghana. They have collected over 2000kg of textile waste and produced over 5000 pairs of shoes since its inception. The first aim was to help with unemployment in their city by creating something with the cheap resources available locally. A businessman and a friend who works as a shoemaker began developing this venture. They search for the cheapest material which is discarded textile waste and transform it into something valuable with awareness of sustainability and the need to reduce waste's negative environmental impact [10]. They travel to the secondhand market to collect and sometimes buy discarded textiles, which they then bring into the factory. Jeans are repurposed into shoes. Soles are made using car tyres and conveyor belts.

a. Children's toys. Rosario Hevia Ecocitex, Chile said after having her second kid, she realised that much children's clothing goes to garbage. She devised a mechanism in which people could buy, exchange, or donate unwanted children's garments. After researching the environmental situation, she began seeking for remedies. After much experimentation, they upcycled the worn-out clothing into products such as children's toys and pencil cases, as well as yarns [10]. A staff of incarcerated women cuts and separates the clothes by colour. They sell yarn and have a product line that includes mats, blankets, cushions and headgear. The residual debris is utilised to stuff pillows or boxing punchbags.

b. Rugs. Ume Kulsum Hussain founder of East Rugs, Pakistan, turned the window upside down. She once visited her father's textile mill and saw thousands of tonnes of garbage produced. She began to visualise the garbage produced by hundreds of factories. After graduating in textile design, she came up with the idea of manufacturing carpets out of garbage. She collects waste from manufacturers and employs a crew of five women to sort it, chop

it up, and turn it into yarn. Then they began weaving rugs on handlooms. Her objective was successful, and people became aware that the amount of textile waste is an issue [10].

c. Bricks: Clarisse Merlet, the founder of FabBRICK, uses bricks to produce furniture or partition walls. These bricks are not ordinary bricks, but recycled abandoned textiles transformed into an insulating, structural and aesthetically pleasing building material. While studying, Clarisse Merlet became concerned about pollution in the building business. She began constructing bricks out of mostly textiles, plastic bottles, and cardboard. To achieve a satisfactory result, the textile is squeezed in a mould and then crushed into fibres and little pieces of cloth.

3 Result and Discussion

Fast fashion trends in the textile industry have led to increased fibre consumption and waste generation, demanding research into sustainable recycling technologies. Most systems evaluate post-industrial textile waste and suggest chemical and biological recycling alternatives [11]. The global population growth, improved living circumstances, and shorter product life cycles have all contributed to an increasing textile waste problem. Issues include huge corporations, garbage collection challenges, and pollutants. Increased customer awareness is required for fiber-to-fiber recycling [12].

The textile sector emits the most pollutants in the world. Textile recycling is becoming seen as an important way to minimise pollution and greenhouse gas emissions. The textile business uses a lot of water, energy, and chemicals, which have a big influence on the environment. Cotton and polyester are the two most widely used fibres in the textile industry, accounting for more than 85% of global fibre output. Natural fibres can emit methane and CO₂ into the atmosphere and take weeks to years to disintegrate [13]. Synthetic textiles, on the other hand, are difficult to breakdown and can leach harmful compounds into groundwater and adjacent soil.

Textile production and consumption must be improved in order to implement fiber-to-fiber recycling. Currently, fabrics are not designed for recycling. Producers must prioritise 'design for recycling' textile materials. Increased monofilaments could boost recycling, while blended textiles are a major concern due to declining recycling rates. Less complex blending is feasible for textile fibers. Composting, biogas production, and reprocessing in industrial reactors are examples of alternative waste management solutions [14].

The sustainability component leads to a high acceptability of home furnishings created from textile waste because the sustainable market is growing by the day, and the demand for unique value-added product is gaining traction in the trend market. The fashion industry is undergoing a shift towards sustainable fashion, aiming to reduce its environmental and social impact by utilizing eco-friendly and socially responsible textiles. Biodegradable synthetic fibres, made from natural resources like corn or potato starch, are being developed to reduce environmental impact while maintaining durability and performance. The use of biodegradable synthetic fibres can reduce environmental impact while maintaining durability and performance. The textile sector's influence on the environment and workers can be enhanced by sustainable practices, with consumers driving change [15]. Fast fashion has increased textile product discarded, prompting the development of recycling systems to convert waste into raw materials for value-added products, aiming to reduce environmental impact.

By implementing a sustainable marketing plan, you can strike a delicate balance between promoting products or services and ostensibly minimising harmful short and long-term effects on the environment, society, and economy. Several advantages of sustainable marketing include improved brand reputation, consumer loyalty, shared employee beliefs, and the exploration of new areas for ongoing innovation.

4 Conclusion

The problem of textile waste in India requires a complex solution. India's textile sector can become a global leader in social and environmental responsibility by embracing circularity, promoting sustainable production, educating consumers, developing infrastructure, and supporting innovation. In addition to protecting the environment, this change will strengthen communities, provide new business opportunities, minimise textile industry waste, and ensure a more sustainable future for both the sector and the country as a whole. Reusing pre-consumer textile waste is essential nowadays. This research study represents a minor step towards the community's long-term growth. Pre-consumer textile waste can come from the garment and upholstery sectors. Designs were developed and assessed. The creation was carried out based on the evaluation. Marketers praised the idea of recycling textile waste to repurpose fibre and create home goods. Recycling and sustainable development were also promoted. The only answers to textile industrial waste are reuse, recycling, and reduction, and we must treat it as vital as any other

industrial activity in the textile industry. Waste recycling systems are examined from an economic standpoint, and they can be processed at several levels. The technological modalities for processing fibrous waste, which rely on mechanical, physical, and chemical means of influencing the material, are briefly outlined. Based on the findings, it was determined that recycling can be utilised to successfully and economically reuse not only industrial waste but also other fibrous materials and products that have become obsolete in industry.

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